

The Role of Human Resource Competence, Business Innovation and Working Capital Affected by Intervening Variables of Work Ethics on The Sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the direct and indirect influence of HR competence, business innovation and working capital on the business sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali Province through the HR work ethic variable as an intervening variable. The research method in this study is a quantitative descriptive research method using path analysis using PLS 3.0. In this study the independent variable is the variable HR competence, business innovation and working capital, while for the dependent variable is sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali Province and the intervening variable is HR work ethic. The data obtained in this study is the business data of Rural Banks in Bali amounting to 134 Rural Banks, the object of which is the manager of 134 Rural Banks in Bali as a population, the research uses the PLS 3.0 path analysis method. The conclusion that can be drawn from the results of this study is that partially only the HR competency variable, business innovation and working capital affect the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali and partially only the HR competency variable that affects the work ethic of Rural Bank employees in Bali, while simultaneously the variables of HR competence, business innovation and working capital have an effect on the variable of sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali through the work ethic of Rural Bank employees in Bali as an intervening variable (intervening factor). It can be explained that Rural Banks in Bali must be able to create new breakthroughs in their work system,

Keywords: *hr competency, business innovation, working capital, work ethic, sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

Today's business world if you want to run a sustainable business, you need what is called a resource, the resources in question are resources in the production section, such as the presence of raw materials (materials) and production processes and factory machines, sources of capital or money originating from investment, and business owner's capital, the investment can be in the form of cash investments, in the form of shares and non-cash investments. Besides that, there are also human resources, these human resources are the parties who work in the company or the parties that drive the company. company operations. To create a lasting business, it takes a lot of human resources who have the ability according to their field of work when they want to develop an organizational structure based on the company's vision and mission. Existing human resources must be properly selected and tested for their abilities and competencies so that later when they want to move the company, they are able to work seriously and responsibly. The business world requires a transformation or paradigm shift that

originally used old-fashioned thinking turned into forward-looking thinking, today's business world, if it wants to last forever, must create a new innovation, both in terms of the production process, as well as in terms of providing positions in the organizational structure, This position adjustment is carried out to balance itself with existing conditions and trends, so that the company can make adjustments to the circumstances and conditions to change the paradigm, especially the paradigm regarding job descriptions. (Onufrey & Bergek, 2021). In the process of transformation to adjust conditions in the field of human resources, human resources are needed who not only have long knowledge of the job description they will be working on, but also understand and comply with the work procedures to be made, so that later these HR will be able to translate each procedure. and the duties and responsibilities that he will carry, so that he will be able to adapt well to the work atmosphere, work environment, and things that make him able to complete the job wisely. (Biron et al., 2021) Capital knowledge alone is not enough to

balance themselves and adapt to the way of working that will be enforced by the company, but HR also requires qualified competencies, as well as a good work ethic, so that he can control himself against something that will disturb him, as well as something that hinder him, so that he can have a locus of control over himself and his soul, thus enabling him to be wise and mature in overcoming all problems that hinder the work he does.

The work ethic in question is an employee who must have high manners when dealing with management, have good manners at work, both when entering the office and returning home from work, as well as an attitude when the worker receives a job description from the management, accepts work procedures, and when accepting the duties and responsibilities assigned to him, job descriptions or positions carried out in the organizational structure. This work ethic can also be seen from the attitude of workers when they want to complete work, work procedures and work creativity, so that this work ethic plays an important role in increasing the ability of human resources to drive business so that sustainability can be realized in the future. The transformation process for sustainability is also carried out by increasing working capital, this working capital plays a very vital role in the movement, pace, and expansion of business in order to improve the transformation process for the better, with this working capital business innovation can be easily carried out, rewards Human resources who excel can also be given, as well as increasing business creativity can be easily implemented, so that later the business to be developed can adapt well to things that can change the work system and also the production process, so that the company can survive the onslaught of competitors who modifying the business and conducting business innovation wisely and comprehensively. The process of change or transformation carried out is not carried out by one industry sector alone, but nowadays various industrial sectors need a paradigm shift and the transformation process to be better and more mature, one of which is the banking industry, especially Rural Banks. again using the old method or system that allows Rural Banks to channel credit to the public without looking at the customer's track record and always targeting the maximum amount of credit. This old paradigm can no longer be carried out by Rural

Banks, because in reality the amount of return expected is not optimal.

However, along with changes in the external environment, a rapid and radical change from an offline system to a digital one, Rural Banks must be able to create and create a new paradigm of lending activities so that later they will not experience losses and even tend to be unable to operate again, when the repayment process is carried out. funds from loans disbursed, then Rural Banks need innovations that will be able to create a system that can change the workings of the Rural Banks, this innovation requires competent human resources in accordance with the field of work and able to interpret and translate job descriptions and systems. existing work. By presenting competent resources, it is hoped that these resources have a work ethic that is in accordance with the job description, procedures and work systems that exist at Rural Banks, so that they can follow the rhythm of Rural Banks' work, so that later the human resources owned are able to provide good assessment and analysis to the Rural Bank's customers who need to be given credit so that later when credit is disbursed, it can return in a timely manner. In addition, the working capital of Rural Banks must be able to provide the ability of Rural Banks to always improve the quality of funding and increase the availability of funds to cover the lack of funds from the results of lending and cover the shortage of funds in the event of non-performing financing, so that with increased working capital, operational Rural Bank's business can continue in the coming year, so as to be able to provide assurance that Rural Banks are the right institutions or businesses in the credit distribution process. Bali Province is one of the provinces that has businesses, both MSMEs and medium and large businesses in the tourism sector, there are 409,858 businesses dominated by small and medium enterprises (MSMEs), these business operations require capital, so an institution is needed as a place for distributing funds or capital. for business through credit. This makes the Bali Provincial Government need a credit distribution business institution, namely the Rural Bank. To find out the description of the number of Rural Banks from 2020-2021 can be seen in Table 1 below: Bali Province is one of the provinces that has businesses, both MSMEs and medium and large businesses in the tourism sector, there are

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Table 1 Number of Rural Banks in Bali Province 2010-2021

Year	Number of Rural Banks (Unit)
2010	65
2011	81
2012	93
2013	99
2014	107
2015	115
2016	123
2017	127
2018	124
2019	130
2020	144
2021	134

Source: BPS Prov. Bali, 2021

Based on Table 1 above, it can be explained that the number of Rural Banks in Bali in the 2010-2021 range tends to decrease, had increased in 2020, in the following year (2021) it fell again because some of the Rural Banks experienced a decline. bankruptcy because they are no longer able to channel credit due to the minimal availability of funds and there are also mergers with other Rural Banks. This situation greatly affects the quality and quantity of credit to be disbursed. This is due to the inability of Rural Banks in the Province of Bali to adapt to changing conditions and situations in the internal environment, so that the old paradigm of Rural Banks in Bali is still trapped, which only targets the distribution of the maximum amount of credit, which affects the sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali. By still applying the old paradigm, it can affect the ability of Rural Bank HR in translating

every work procedure, HR tends to be rigid and not creative, and the capabilities and competencies they have do not come out due to limited movement, as well as the rigidity of the Rural Bank's business in responding to changes and changes. rapid transformation. This causes the existing work ethic to be inconsistent and in line with what is expected by Rural Banks. Besides that, The purpose of this study is to determine the direct and indirect influence of HR competence, business innovation and working capital on the business sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali Province through the HR work ethic variable as an intervening variable.

LITERATURE REVIEW

HR Competence

(Yu et al., 2017) HR competencies are related to the basic characteristics possessed by

HR, so that with these characteristics, it is expected to increase the capabilities and capabilities possessed in order to increase work productivity.(Barba-Aragon & Jimenez-Jiménez, 2020)states that HR competence is the ability and characteristics that exist in every worker, these abilities and characteristics can be used to improve good and effective work to help businesses become more developed.(Ben Moussa & El Arbi, 2020)states that HR competence is something that is owned related to the knowledge, skills, abilities and personality characteristics that affect the performance of the HR.(Christofi et al., 2019)There are five types or characteristics of these competencies, the types and characteristics of these competencies, namely the existence of motives in work, individual characteristics of workers, self-concept of workers, knowledge of workers in their field of work, and the ability of human resources in their field of work.(Nielsen et al., 2016)the factors that affect the competence of HR are as follows:Skills possessed, Self-confidence, Knowledge possessed, Self-motivation, Intellectual ability, Emotional.

Business Innovation

(Mukherjee et al., 2020)business innovation is the heart of business activities, innovation plays an important role in improving sustainability by establishing new ideas for each business activity that will be undertaken.(Kim & Amran, 2018)Business innovation is a process of creating a new idea, the creation of this idea is carried out to improve the company's ability to change its business system and philosophy in order to improve sustainability.(Alshamsi et al., 2020)Business innovation is the creation of an idea, both in terms of governance, systems, and ways of working that are carried out by the creative team to ensure that the business being run has a new concept and is able to create new products that meet consumer expectations. (Saad & Elshaer, 2020)Business innovation is the process of implementing new ideas, creativity and fresh and new ideas, the creation of new ideas or new ideas is carried out to increase product sales revenue, while improving the existing system in the company for the better.(Tripathi & Bagga, 2020)The types of product innovations are not only in terms of products, but also product innovations that update production processes, systems, work methods in the company's operations..(Xuan Luan & Thanh Tung, 2019)the

factors that influence the increase in business innovation are as follows:The existing system is not appropriate, the working method applied is outdated, the production process is slow, the product is less competitive, the product sales performance is down.

Working capital

(Ahmad & Ahmad, 2018)Working capital is an excess of assets caused by the provision of funds for the company's operational activities, or it can be said that the availability of funds for reserves if operational activities experience problems and cause losses.(Tobing, 2019)working capital is a measurement of the level of liquidity or the availability of company funds intended to increase reserves in case of problems in operational activities.(Hutahayan, 2020)Working capital is net capital which is the difference between current assets and current liabilities which is intended to finance the company's operations and as a reserve to cover the existing lack of capital.(Cunningham et al., 2016)Working capital is something that is used to determine the smooth running of a company's operational activities that can be useful for increasing the availability of funds in the company's operational processes.(Shabri et al., 2020) With sufficient working capital, it is hoped that it will benefit the company to operate economically, efficiently and of course the company will no longer lack capital to increase the company's operational activities.(Sopa et al., 2020)The factors that affect the increase in working capital are as follows: Small amount of assets, little cash turnover, low profits, inefficient work, less smooth liquidity.

Work Ethics

(Brinkerink et al., 2020)Work ethic is a principle value that is firmly held by workers which is intended as a regulator in carrying out work activities.(Best et al., 2021)Work ethics are rules that can change the behavior and attitudes of workers in completing work in accordance with job descriptions, company rules, and in accordance with applicable work procedures.(Donner et al., 2020)Work ethics is something that has values and norms and rules that are intended for workers so that workers have proper behavior and attitudes in completing their duties and responsibilities properly.(Lena & Anatan, 2020)Work ethics are attitudes, views and habits that are characteristic of employees, these attitudes must be adjusted and adapted to the

company's work culture.(Moşteanu, 2020)work ethic is closely related to the rules and regulations that make him participate and adapt to the company's work culture, workers can no longer arbitrarily complete their work and must follow the company's work rules and procedures.(Kato & Charoenrat, 2018)The factors that affect work ethics are as follows:The absence of clear work standards, complicated work procedures, low employee work discipline, work procedures from workers who are often wrong

Sustainability

(Berger et al., 2020) stated that sustainability is the ability of a business to be able to maintain its business operations by creating a smart idea so that its business can compete with others.(Young, 2020) explained that sustainability is the effort of the business unit in carrying out the continuation of its operational activities in order to be able to survive the invasion of other similar businesses that have different ideas and strategies from our business.(He & Sun, 2020)Sustainability is the ability of a business to maintain the level of production of its products by increasing creativity and innovation that is different from competitors, so that its business can survive the onslaught of other businesses.(Raab, 2020) sustainability of a business unit can be carried out by implementing a new innovation in every activity and production process, as well as business systems, this is done so that businesses can survive rapid changes, both changes in the internal and external environment.(Stahl et al., 2019) The factors that

affect the sustainability of a business are as follows: new ideas and ideas for the business system being carried out, transformation of business operations, changes in competitor strategies, changes in conditions and situations in the internal and external environment rapidly.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study the independent variable is the variable HR competence, business innovation and working capital, while for the dependent variable is sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali Province and the intervening variable is HR work ethic.The research method used is descriptive quantitative,(Kurniawan & Wahyuningsih, 2018) quantitative descriptive analysis is an analysis or research method used to analyze changes that occur between one variable and another variable, then conclusions are made in the form of any factors that influence between variables. For data analysis carried out by using path analysis using the PLS 3.0 program(Cheung et al., 2016). The population of this study is the business data of Rural Banks in Bali Province in 2021 as many as 134 business units whose research objects for the distribution of the questionnaire are the manager of 134 Rural Banks in Bali. The sampling technique using the census method,(Wang et al., 2020)sampling technique by census is a sampling technique whose sampling is based on a predetermined number of populations. The number of samples in this study is the number of Rural Banks in Bali Province, amounting to 134.

RESEARCH RESULT

The PLS output results are as follows:

Convergent Validity

(Mandhani et al., 2020) Convergent validity is a test carried out to get the value of outer loading whose value is greater than the

significance level of 0.7, the results of this convergent validity test can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2 Convergent Validity Test

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
HR Competency (X1)	KSDM1	0.834
	KSDM 2	0.841
	KSDM 3	0.825
	KSDM 4	0.830
	KSDM 5	0.767
	KSDM 6	0.772
Business Innovation (X2)	Inovus 1	0.804
	Inovus 2	0.734
	Inovus 3	0.749
	Inovus 4	0.855
	Inovus 5	0.828
Working Capital (X3)	MK 1	0.731
	MK 2	0.754

	MK 3	0.856
	MK 4	0.863
	MK 5	0.740
Sustainability (Y)	Bus 1	0.873
	Bus 2	0.739
	Bus 3	0.780
	Bus 4	0.897
Work Ethics (Z)	EK 1	0.742
	EK 2	0.818
	EK 3	0.765
	EK 4	0.784

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on Table 2 above, it can be explained that the outer loading indicator value of each variable in the form of the outer loading value for all variables is greater than 0.7, all **Average Variant Extracted(AVE)**

The average variant extract test was carried out to determine the validity and reliability

existing data distributions have valid data distributions.

of the data with the condition that the AVE value was greater than 0.5. The results of the AVE can be seen in Table 3 below:

Table 3 AVE . Test

Variable	AVE
HR Competency (X1)	0.677
Business Innovation (X2)	0.687
Working Capital (X3)	0.554
Sustainability (Y)	0.632
Work Ethics (Z)	0.687

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on Table 2 above, it can be explained that the results of the Average Variant Extracted (AVE) test for all variables are greater than a significance value of 0.5, all data distributions in each variable are accurate and valid.

Composite Reliability

The value of composite reliability in the data analysis carried out can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4 Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability
HR Competency (X1)	0.883
Business Innovation (X2)	0.827
Working Capital (X3)	0.747
Sustainability (Y)	0.892
Work Ethics (Z)	0.850

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

In accordance with Table 4 above, it can be concluded that the composite reliability test results of each variable have a significance value greater than 0.6, the data turnover of each variable is feasible and reliable.

Path Coefficient Test

The results of the test data for testing the path coefficient (R Square) of each variable can be seen in Table 5 to Table 11 below:

Table 5 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
HR Competency (X1)	0.745
Sustainability(Y)	0.698

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 5, it can be explained that the R Square value of the HR competency variable is 0.745, the percentage increase in HR competence by 74.5% can be explained by the

sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali and the rest can be explained by other variables not examined by researchers of 25 ,5%

Table 6 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
Business Innovation (X2)	0.771
Sustainability (Y)	0.760

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 6, it can be explained that the R Square value of the business innovation variable is 0.771, the percentage of increasing business innovation by 77.1% can be explained by

the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali and the rest can be explained by other variables not examined by researchers of 22 ,9%

Table 7 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
Working Capital (X3)	0.737
Sustainability (Y)	0.740

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 7, it can be explained that the R Square value of the working capital variable is 0.737, the percentage increase in working capital of 73.7% can be explained by the variable

of sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali and the rest can be explained by other variables not examined by researchers of 26 ,3%.

Table 8 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
HR Competency (X1)	0.744
Work Ethics (Z)	0.767

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 8, it can be explained that the R Square value of the HR competency variable is 0.744, the percentage of HR competency increasing by 74.4% can be explained by the work

ethic variable and the rest can be explained by other variables not examined by the researcher by 25.6%.

Table 9 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
Business Innovation (X2)	0.524
Work Ethics (Z)	0.570

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 9 it can be explained that the R Square value of the business innovation variable of Rural Banks in Bali is 0.524, the percentage of increasing business novation of

Rural Banks in Bali by 52.4% can be explained by the work ethic variable and the rest can be explained by other variables that are not studied by researchers amounted to 47.6%.

Table 10 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
Working Capital (X3)	0.558
Work Ethics (Z)	0.527

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 10, it can be explained that the R Square value of the modal variable Work of 0.558, the percentage of capital increase Work of 55.8% can be explained by the work ethic variable

and the rest can be explained by other variables not examined by the researcher at 44.2%.

Table 11 Test R Square

Variable	R Square
Work Ethics (Z)	0.770
Sustainability (Y)	0.756

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2022

Based on table 11, it can be explained that the R Square value of the work ethic variable is 0.770, the percentage of increasing work ethic by 77% can be explained by the variable of sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali and the rest

can be explained by other variables not examined by researchers by 23%.

Hypothesis testing

The results of hypothesis testing from this study can be seen in Table 12 below:

Table 12 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Influence	T-Statistics	P-Value	Results
H1	HR competence for sustainability	4,652	0.000	Received
H2	Business Innovation for sustainability	7,215	0.001	Received
H3	Working capital for sustainability	5,172	0.000	Received
H4	HR competence on work ethics	3,247	0.002	Received
H5	Business Innovation on work ethics	-6.322	0.211	Rejected
H6	Working capital on the quality of work ethics	-4,307	0.345	Received
H7	HR competence on sustainability with work ethics as an intervening variable	4,234	0.001	Received
H8	Business Innovation on sustainability with work ethics as an intervening variable	6,827	0.002	Received
H9	Working capital on sustainability with work ethic as an intervening variable	5,451	0.000	received

Source: Data Processing Results With PLS 3.0, 2021

Based on Table 12 above, partially only the competence variable of HR, business innovation and working capital affect the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali and in proportion only the HR competence variable that affects the work ethic of Rural Bank employees in Bali, while Simultaneous HR competency variables, business innovation and working capital have an effect on the sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali through the work ethics of Rural Bank employees in Bali as an intervening variable (intervening factor).

The results of the t-test of the HR competency variable, with a t-test value of 4.652, greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the HR competency variable has a significant effect on the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali. (Barba-Aragon & Jimenez-Jiménez, 2020) states that competent human resources are valuable assets in the company to encourage the improvement of company operations, competent employees will be able to improve business performance through their work for the benefit of the business, so that the business will be productive and generate profits. improve business sustainability in the future.

DISCUSSION

The results of the t-test of the HR competency variable, with a t-test value of 3.247, which is greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the HR competency variable has a significant effect on the employee work ethic variable.(Brinkerink et al., 2020)Employees who have competence will be able to apply good working principles in the company, will maintain a good and honest attitude, so that the employee will be able to translate work rules and procedures and be adjusted to the job description given to the employee.

The results of the t-test for the HR competency variable, with a t-test value of 4.234, greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that HR competence has a significant effect on the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali through the work ethic variable as an intervening variable, (Berger et al., 2020) employees who have competence and ability can improve their performance by willing to apply their abilities based on work rules and procedures, with the adaptation process it is hoped that employees will be able to complete their work to encourage better company performance, so that the business will be sustainable and continue in the future.

The results of the t-test of the business innovation variable, with a t-test value of 7.215, greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the business innovation variable has a significant effect on the sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali.(Kim & Amran, 2018)stated that a business that always innovates that is different from similar businesses, it will easily improve renewal and create products that meet customer expectations, with new ideas and new ideas from business operations, it is hoped that businesses can adapt to changing environmental conditions. , later this company will still exist and its business will continue in the future.

The results of the t-test of the business innovation variable, with a t-test value of -6.322, which is smaller than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the business innovation variable has no significant effect on employee work ethics.(Tripathi & Bagga, 2020)stated that efforts to innovate on business are not always able to implement and discipline employees to follow existing rules and procedures, management's inability to create work procedures is feared will

make employees' work ethics decrease and interfere with efforts to improve their performance, so that the income to be received is not on target or even tends to decrease. This has an impact on the doubts of business owners whether this business will continue or not.

The results of the t-test of the business innovation variable, with a t-test value of 6.827, greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the business innovation variable has a significant effect on the sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali through the employee work ethic variable as an intervening variable, research(Young, 2020)stated that the existence of innovation in business also affects changes in procedures and work procedures, these changes must be adjusted to the capabilities of human resources and human resource development, so that business performance improvements can be directed and sustainable, as a result, business sustainability must be carried out so that existing employment opportunities can be maximized..

The results of the t-test of the working capital variable, with a t-test value of 5.172, greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the working capital variable has a significant effect on the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali.(Tobing, 2019)working capital will be able to help the smooth operation of the company, as well as cover the losses suffered by the company by increasing working capital, the continuity of the existing business will continue in the future..

The results of the t-test of the working capital variable, with a t-test value of -4.307, which is smaller than the 0.05 degree of significance, which means that the working capital variable has no significant effect on the employee work ethic variable.(Best et al., 2021)working capital has nothing to do with changes and the establishment of work procedures, working capital is related to the ability of the business to assist efforts for the business to continue to operate and improve its performance to generate profits and income..

The results of the t-test of the working capital variable, with a t-test value of 5.451, greater than a significance degree of 0.05, which means that the working capital variable has a significant effect on the sustainability variable of Rural Banks in Bali through the employee work ethic variable as an intervening variable,(Stahl et

al., 2019) Working capital greatly affects the ability of the management to create innovation, so that it can change the work system, as well as employee work procedures and rules, if the employee can adapt well, then he will be able to encourage his performance and also the company's performance, so that with the optimism of performance can increase, then the effort is expected to continue in the future.

Conclusion

The conclusion that can be drawn from the results of this study is that partially only the competence of HR, business innovation and working capital variables affect the sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali and in proportion only the competence of HR variables that affect the work ethics of Rural Bank employees in Bali. , while simultaneously the variables of HR competence, business innovation and working capital have an effect on the sustainability of Rural Banks in Bali through the work ethics of Rural Bank employees in Bali as an intervening variable (intervening factor). Based on the results of the study, it can be explained that Rural Banks in Bali must be able to create new breakthroughs in their work system,

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